

XROTOR

X-shaped Radical Offshore Wind Turbine for Overall Cost of Energy Reduction

D3.1

Definition of operational strategy

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About X-ROTOR

X-ROTOR: “X-shaped Radical Offshore wind Turbine for Overall cost of energy Reduction” is a Horizon 2020 funded project which aims to develop a disruptive new offshore wind turbine concept.

The X-ROTOR project is led by University of Strathclyde (UK) in partnership with Norwegian University of Science and Technology (Norway), Delft University of Technology (Netherlands), University College Cork (Ireland), Fundacion Cener National Renewable Energy Centre (Spain) and GE Renovables España (Spain).

As the effects of climate change are becoming ever more visible, Europe has raised its target for the amount of energy it consumes from renewable sources from the previous goal of 27% to 32% by 2030. Offshore wind energy can play a key role in achieving the EU target and contribute to the required 40% reduction in CO₂ emissions. However, to achieve the previously mentioned targets the cost of offshore wind must be reduced. The X-ROTOR concept provides a direct route to drastically reducing both capital and operating costs of energy from offshore wind.

The project runs for three years from January 2021, during which time, the concept will be developed through a holistic consideration of technical, cost, environmental and socio-economic impact aspects.

If proven feasible, X-ROTOR will, as a disruptive new offshore wind turbine concept, create new opportunities for the European wind energy industry and play an important role maintaining the EU’s position as global technological leader in renewable energy, reducing greenhouse gas emissions and decarbonising the EU economy.

For more information see <https://xrotor-project.eu>

Description of the deliverable and its purpose

This deliverable discusses the options available in the operational strategy of the X-Rotor turbine, and presents a feasible control strategy for the full operational envelope of the turbine. The strategy primarily aims to maximum energy capture whilst accounting for limits on secondary rotor operation and actuator constraints. The control strategy of the secondary rotors has been significantly modified in order to limit the power swings present in the powertrain.

List of acronyms

VAWT	Vertical Axis Wind Turbine
HAWT	Horizontal Axis Wind Turbine
PMSG	Permanent Magnet Synchronous Generator

1 Introduction

The X-Rotor consists of an approximately X-Shaped vertical axis wind turbine (VAWT), henceforth referred to as the primary rotor, with small horizontal axis wind turbines (HAWTs) attached to the tips of the lower blades, henceforth referred to as the secondary rotors. Unlike traditional HAWTs, there is no electrical or mechanical power take off from the primary rotor shaft and power take off completed entirely from the secondary rotors.

The incident wind speed on the secondary rotors is approximately equal to the primary rotor tip speed, significantly increasing the power density and allowing the rotors to have a small swept area. In turn, the small rotor radius allows the secondary rotors to operate at a high rotational speed, facilitating the use of small permanent magnet synchronous generators (PMSGs), with only 4 pole pairs, in a direct drive configuration. In addition to the implied capital cost benefits of forgoing a mechanical gearbox or a large multi-pole generator [1], there are significant operations and maintenance cost benefits expected from locating the secondary rotors close the ocean surface and eliminating the need for large jack up vessels for power-train failures [2].

The operational strategy of a wind turbine defines the operating points at which it operates assuming perfect control. Consequently, the operational strategy determines the energy capture of the turbine and the likely loading of the turbine components and is important in determining the cost of energy from the wind turbine.

Traditional HAWT wind turbines have converged on a variable speed, variable pitch control with rotors operating in maximum power point tracking in below rated conditions and pitching to feather in above rated conditions to hold the rotor at constant rotational speed and torque output. In addition, pre-emptive pitch scheduling is sometimes applied in order to limit the maximum pitch rates around rated wind speed. In low wind speeds, the control strategy is modified to include a minimum rotor speed and, thereby, avoid inefficient power conversion in the power-train [3].

The X-Rotor primary rotor is controlled in a similar manner to a traditional HAWT, operating in maximum power point tracking mode in below rated windspeeds and in constant speed mode in above rated wind speeds with pitch control of the upper blades. Despite this similarity, the control of the X-Rotor is significantly more complex due to the secondary rotors. The operating point of the primary rotor is dictated by the aerodynamic torque on the primary rotor with the counterbalancing torque arising from the thrust on the secondary rotors [4] rather than the reaction torque from a generator. The operating point of the secondary rotors is dictated by the incident wind speed on the secondary rotors and the torque provided by the secondary rotor drive-train. It is this two-level control problem that is discussed in this deliverable report.

The report consists of 4 further sections. Section 2 provides a more detailed discussion of the control of the X-Rotor and the determination of equilibrium operating points, making relevant comparisons to the control of traditional HAWTs for clarity. Section 3 defines the different operational zones of the X-Rotor and discusses the control options in each of these zones. Section 4 provides the definition of the X-Rotors operational strategy, and section 5 Presents the concluding statements.

2 Control of the X-Rotor

2.1 Comparison of X-Rotor and HAWT

2.1.1 Rotor aerodynamics

In the case of the X-Rotor, the aerodynamics can be discussed in terms of the primary and secondary rotors separately. The primary rotor rotates around its vertical axis. Each blade therefore sees a large azimuthal variation in the angle of attack and consequently in the forces/torques on the blade. Summing across the two blades, this leads to large 2P oscillations in the aerodynamic torque on the primary rotor. In terms of the secondary rotors, the incident windspeed on the secondary rotors is given by

$$U_I = \Omega_p R_P + U_0 \sin(\theta_p) = U_0 (\lambda_p + \sin(\theta_p)) \tag{1}$$

and therefore has a strong 1P oscillation. Here Ω represents the rotor speed, R represents the rotor radius, U_0 represents the incoming windspeed and λ represents the tip speed ratio. The subscript on X_p indicates that it is a primary rotor variable. To maintain a constant tip speed ratio, the secondary rotor speed must vary with the azimuth angle of the primary rotor blade to which it is attached. Since the incident wind speeds on the two secondary rotors have a phase difference of π , the summed power output have 2P oscillations with a considerably smaller amplitude than the 1P oscillations in the incident wind speeds.

The primary rotor power coefficient is a function of the primary rotor tip speed ratio and pitch offset, see Figure 1. It is obtained using the 2D actuator cylinder model presented in [5]. The secondary rotor power and thrust coefficients are shown in figure 2.

Figure 1: Primary rotor power coefficient as a function of pitch angle and tip speed ratio

Figure 2: Secondary rotor thrust and power coefficient as a function of secondary rotor tip speed ratio

2.1.2 Available control actuators

A traditional HAWT rotor has three primary control actions, the collective pitch angle of the rotor blades, the generator reaction torque, and the yaw drive. The yaw drive is used to maintain alignment between the rotor plane and the incoming windspeed. In below rated wind speeds, rotor speed is regulated through varying the generator reaction torque that acts on the rotor. In above rated wind speeds, rotor speed is regulated by varying the blade pitch angles and, thereby, the aerodynamic torque whilst the generator is regulated to maintain a constant reaction torque and thereby constant generator power. As the rotor aerodynamics are relatively uniform over a single rotor revolution, both the rotor torque and pitch angle are described with a single value in the operational strategy, rather than being dependent on the azimuth angle.

The X-Rotor has two primary control actions, pitch angle of the upper blades and thrust on the secondary rotors. In below rated conditions, the thrust from the secondary rotors is controlled to provide the desired retarding torque on the primary rotor, thereby regulating the primary rotor speed. In above rated conditions, the upper blades of the primary rotor are pitched to regulate the aerodynamic torque on the primary rotor and, thereby, the rotor speed. A yaw drive is not required as the primary rotor rotates around the vertical axis and is therefore insensitive to the direction of the incoming wind.

2.1.3 Power take off

In a traditional HAWT, the power take-off is accomplished by a generator connected to the rotor. Modern offshore wind turbines typically employ a fully rated power converter allowing the reaction torque demanded by a controller to be readily provided by the generator. In a direct drive configuration, the efficiency of power conversion is primarily dictated by the efficiency of the generator, the cost of efficiency is an increase in the mass and cost of the generator, and a design trade off is typically reached, with approximately 96% efficiency accepted as a reasonable value before further conversion by the power electronics [3]. The efficiency of power conversion is also speed dependent, with the efficiency of power conversion dropping significantly at rotational speeds well below the rated speed.

In the case of the X-Rotor, power take-off is accomplished through the secondary rotors. Consider the turbine operating in a constant wind speed. There is no equilibrium operating point as the primary rotor torque and secondary rotor thrust are never in balance as both vary substantially with azimuth angle. However, the turbine can be controlled such that they balance over a complete rotation. The operating strategy that maximises energy capture is to maintain the secondary rotors at constant tip speed ratio. The efficiency of power conversion from the primary rotor to the secondary rotors is

$$\eta = \frac{N_s \overline{P_s}}{\Omega_p R \overline{T_s}} = \frac{\overline{(\lambda_p + \sin(\theta_p))^3 C_{P_s}}}{\lambda_p (\lambda_p + \sin(\theta_p))^2 C_{T_s}} \quad (2)$$

where N_s is the number of secondary rotors, P represents the aerodynamic power captured by a rotor, T represents the aerodynamic thrust on the rotor, \overline{X} represents the average of the variable, X , over a single primary rotor rotation, the subscript X_s refers to variables corresponding to the secondary rotor, and C_P and C_T represent the aerodynamic power and thrust coefficient of the rotor. The maximum efficiency with the secondary rotors operating at a constant tip speed ratio has efficiency

$$\eta = \frac{C_{P_s}}{C_{T_s}} \left(\frac{1 + 1.5\lambda_p^{-2}}{1 + 0.5\lambda_p^{-2}} \right) \quad (3)$$

Whilst, from the perspective of maximising generated power, it might be attractive to always operate the secondary rotors at their optimal tip speed ratio, this would be subject to constraints on the range of rotor speeds arising from power conversion requirements. In this case, η , the ratio of power and thrust coefficient for the secondary rotor, would vary as a function of the secondary rotor tip speed ratio, see Figure 3.

Figure 3: Secondary rotor power coefficient by thrust coefficient, a close proxy for conversion efficiency, as a function of secondary rotor tip speed ratio

2.2 Equilibrium operation of the Primary rotor

As previously mentioned, the torque of the primary rotor of the X-Rotor is never in equilibrium with the combined thrust from the secondary rotors. However, their mean values over a rotation can be balanced and interpreted to define pseudo steady state operating conditions. For such a steady state operating point

$$\frac{1}{2} \rho A_p R_p U_0^2 C_{Qp}(\lambda_p, \beta_p) = N_s R_s \frac{1}{2} \rho A_s \overline{U_I^2 C_{Ts}(\lambda_s)}. \quad (4)$$

where ρ represents the density of air, A represents the rotor area, β represents the rotor pitch angle and C_Q represents the revolution averaged torque coefficient $C_Q = C_p/\lambda$. When the primary rotor is operated far from stall, for a given wind speed the aerodynamic torque decreases as the rotor speed (and hence tip speed ratio) increases. Conversely, the incident wind speed on the secondary rotors increases as the primary rotor speed increases, see (1). For a windspeed of 12m/s, the mean primary rotor aerodynamic torque and the retarding torque from the secondary rotors as a function of the primary rotor speed are depicted in Figure 4.

The intersection of the mean primary rotor aerodynamic torque and secondary rotor induced retarding torque curves in Figure 4 represents a stationary operating point. With the proviso that the dynamics are locally stable in some sense as would be the case in below rated operation, the operating point of the turbine returns to the stationary operating point when displaced. (With a displacement to a higher primary rotor speed, the primary rotor torque is decreased but the thrust and the counteracting torque from the secondary rotors is increased as the induced wind speed acting on the secondary rotors is increased. Consequently, there is a torque imbalance acting on the primary rotor causing its rotor speed to reduce. Similarly, with a displacement to a lower primary rotor speed, there is a torque imbalance acting on the primary rotor causing its rotor speed to increase.)

The previous proviso that the dynamics are locally stable is not a priori the case when pitching to control the primary rotor speed in above rated wind speed. Whether the blades are pitched nose-in (positive pitching) or nose-out (negative pitching), the angle of attack on the blades is inevitably sufficiently large that airflow becomes detached and the aerodynamic damping negative over a significant rotational sector. However, with negative pitching, the positive damping contributions

outweigh the negative damping ones and are sufficiently great that the blade dynamics can be considered essentially stable as required. Consequently, negative pitching is employed to control the X-rotor turbine in above rated wind speed

Figure 4: Primary rotor aerodynamic torque and resultant torque from the secondary rotors as a function of primary rotor speed at a windspeed of 12m/s

Due to the gradients of the mean primary rotor aerodynamic torque and retarding secondary rotor aerodynamic torque curves, any uncertainty in the primary and/or secondary rotor aerodynamics would only lead to a small change in the stationary operating point in Figure 4, i.e. in the intersection of the mean primary rotor aerodynamic torque and retarding secondary rotor torque curves, to which the turbine would naturally migrate. To illustrate this, consider the dashed lines plotted in Figure 4. The changes in aerodynamics these represent are equivalent to a change in pitch from 0° to -5° for the primary rotor and a change in thrust coefficient from 0.35 to 0.4 for the secondary rotors. Any uncertainties in the aerodynamics are unlikely to be as great as these changes, particularly, to the change in the thrust coefficient for the secondary rotors. Figure 4, also, illustrates how the stationary operating point can be changed through changing the primary rotor pitch and/or the secondary rotor thrust.

Figure 5: Primary rotor tip speed ratio in equilibrium operation as a function of primary rotor pitch angle and secondary rotor thrust coefficient

For a set of primary rotor tip speed ratios, equilibrium operating point curves are plotted as functions of primary rotor pitch angle and secondary rotor thrust coefficient in figure 5. The secondary rotor thrust coefficient has a relatively low maximum value, due to its low induction/low tip speed ratio design, see Figure 2. Consequently, the number of possible equilibrium operating points for the primary rotor is significantly limited. In cases where the secondary rotors are not

operated at a constant tip speed ratio, equation (4) must be solved directly to obtain the equilibrium operation position and Figure 5 is not valid. However, it is useful as a conceptual guide.

2.3 Operation of the Secondary rotors

The control of the secondary rotors must be applied under a number of imposed limits. Firstly, in order to maintain high efficiency in the power-train, the secondary rotors must be operated above a minimum rotor speed. Figure 6 shows the efficiency of a secondary rotor power-train as a function of power for the design rotor speed (375rpm), half the design rotor speed, and a quarter of the design rotor speed. This demonstrates the significant loss in efficiency experienced at low rotor speeds. For this reason, the minimum secondary rotor speed is kept above a minimum value.

Figure 6: Efficiency of the secondary rotor powertrain as a function of power angle for rated rotor speed (375rpm) half rated speed, and a quarter of rated speed

Secondly, maximum generator speed/electrical frequency must not exceed an upper limit to ensure that the output voltage of the generator does not exceed its maximum allowable value. Another consideration on the maximum speed of the secondary rotors arises from a constraint on the tip speed, which must not exceed a given value to avoid excessive aero-acoustic emissions and compressibility effects. Finally, depending on the exact design of the power-train, a maximum power limit must be applied to each individual secondary rotor and the combined power output from the secondary rotors.

As in (1), the wind speed incident on the secondary rotor is proportional to the sum of primary rotor tip speed and an azimuthally dependent sinusoidal oscillation at 1P, proportional to the incident wind speed. For the secondary rotors to operate at a constant tip speed ratio, the rotor speed must fluctuate with the same magnitude as the incident wind speed. Additionally, as the power available to the secondary rotors is proportional to the cube of the incident windspeed, the power fluctuations are significantly larger than the speed fluctuations.

It is expected that the generators will be able to operate with reasonably large power fluctuations about the mean, so long as the mean value does not exceed the power rating for the generators. Similarly, the power electronics are expected to be able to deal with moderate power swings above the rated value. However large power swings will require significant over rating and prohibitive increases in the capital cost of the turbine.

The speed of the secondary rotors can either be controlled collectively or individually. Individual control of the secondary rotors requires each secondary rotor to have a dedicated rotor side power converter, whilst collective secondary rotor speed control allows the use of a shared power converter, as shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Potential power train topologies for the X-Rotor. Power train configuration a) facilitates individual speed control of the secondary rotors, whilst configuration b) necessitates collective speed control of the secondary rotors

Individual speed control requires the rotor side converter to be rated sufficiently high to deal with the power swings from the individual secondary rotors, whilst collective speed control allows the single rotor side power converter to take advantage of the averaging effect that occurs as the rotor's power output is summed.

Three secondary rotor control strategies are considered, one with individual secondary rotor speed control, and two with collective secondary rotor speed control:

1. Constant tip speed ratio
In constant tip speed ratio operation, each secondary rotor will be controlled to individually operate at the optimum tip speed ratio. This requires individual speed control and thus utilises the power take off topology described in figure 7a).
2. Constant speed
In constant speed control, the secondary rotor speed will be collectively controlled to be constant. This utilises the power take off topology described in figure 7b).
3. Upwind tracking
In Upwind tracking control, collective speed control is employed, however the secondary rotor which experiences the largest incoming wind speed will be operated at the optimum tip speed ratio.

The motivation for these 3 options is as follows: Option 1 represents the most efficient means of power conversion between the primary and secondary rotors, however the large power swings require over-rated power rotor side power converters. Option 2 utilises the averaging effect of the summing the two output powers together, thereby limiting the range of power fluctuations experienced by the rotor side converter. However, the efficiency of power conversion is significantly lower. Option 3 also employs the averaging effect thus limiting the size of power swings experienced by the rotor side converter. However it is expected to increase the efficiency of power conversion significantly in comparison to Option 2 to almost match Option 1.

Assuming an optimum primary rotor tip speed ratio of 5, a rated wind speed of 11.7m/s, ignoring pre-emptive pitching and speed constraints on the secondary rotors, the power curves for each control option are shown in Figure 8. The power fluctuations experienced by the rotor side power converter in comparison to the mean power at each wind speed is shown in Figure 9.

Although the differences, up to 4%, between the power curves in below rated wind conditions with a tip speed ratio of 5, they are evident in above rated conditions. As the primary rotor tip speed ratio drops in above rated conditions, the power gained using optimal tip speed ratio control is clear. The power sacrificed by moving to upwind speed control is seen to be relatively small.

The power swings experienced by the rotor side power converter are shown to be approximately an order of magnitude larger when constant tip speed ratio control is compared to upwind tracking operation compared. An investigation into the cost saving associated with this significant reduction in the demand on the power train is beyond the scope of this report. However, it is clear that this significant reduction in the swings in input power to the power electronics would result in lower drive-train costs and higher reliability.

As the sacrifice in power capture is relatively small, and the reduction in the maximum power fluctuations is significant, the primary mode of secondary rotor operation considered in this report will be upwind tracking operation (option 3).

Figure 8: Example power curves showing the difference between different modes of operating the secondary rotors

Figure 9: Demonstration of the power swings experienced by the power electronics based of different modes of secondary rotor operation

3 Operating strategy for the X-Rotor

The operational envelope of the X-Rotor wind turbine is split into 5 regions, as shown in Figure 10. In all regions, both secondary rotors have the same fluctuating rotor speed. This rotational speed is set such that the tip speed ratio of the secondary rotor moving upwind into the ambient wind operates at its optimal tip speed ratio, see the upper half of the plot in Figure 11. Of course, the tip speed ratio of the secondary rotor moving down wind does not operate at its optimal tip speed ratio, see the lower half of the plot in Figure 11. The point at which the upper and lower halves of the plots meet, is referred to as the interception point in the following.

In region 1, the interception point is essentially held constant. This has the advantage of keeping the variable speed range to a minimum and thereby maintaining efficient operation. In region 2, the rotor operates in maximum power point tracking mode. In region 3, a pre-emptive pitch regime is

introduced in order to avoid high pitch rates around rated windspeeds. In region 4, the primary rotor is operated in constant speed mode. Finally, in region 5, the primary rotor will continue to be operated in constant speed mode, whilst the secondary rotor power fluctuations will be controlled so to limit the mean power output from the turbine.

Figure 10: Prospective X-Rotor power curve showing the 5 distinct operational regimes

Figure: 11 Secondary rotor torque/speed fluctuations around a single mean operating point at a windspeed of 8m/s

3.1 Low wind speed

The minimum allowable electrical frequency output from the generator is 10Hz, or equivalently 10rad/s. Operating the secondary rotors in upwind tracking mode implies that the minimum rotational speed occurs at $\theta = 0, \pi$, at which point

$$\Omega_s = \frac{\lambda'_s \lambda_p U_0}{R_s}$$

where λ_s represents the nominal tip speed ratio of the secondary rotors (the value of which is tracked as the secondary rotor sweeps upwind). Consequently, the wind speed at which region 1 transitions into region 2 is 4.92m/s. Below this wind speed, the secondary rotors are operated such that the average speed is kept constant at 17.66 rad/s, thereby ensuring that the minimum secondary rotor speed does not drop below the minimum value, 15.7 rad/s. The transition of the secondary rotors into region 1 changes the operation of the primary rotor. The reduction in the mean thrust coefficient leads to an increase in the primary rotor tip speed ratio.

3.2 Maximum power point tracking

The secondary rotors are operated at a nominal tip speed ratio of 3, thereby to maintain the primary rotor at a tip speed ratio of 5. This leads to an efficiency of power conversion of 0.83. As the primary rotor is operating at a power coefficient of 0.48, the overall power coefficient of the two aerodynamic parts of the turbine is 0.4. The rated power of the wind turbine is set to 5MW which corresponds to a rated wind speed of 12m/s if a conservative estimate of the drive-train efficiency of 0.92 is considered (97% for the generator and 95% for the power electronics).

3.3 Pre-emptive pitch

The required pitch action to maintain a constant rotor speed just above rated wind speed is very high. It can be seen from Figure 1, that the primary rotor power coefficient is relatively in-sensitive to the pitch offsets within over an initial range of pitch offsets. Figure 12 shows the required pitch actuation to maintain a constant rotor speed. For this reason, a pre-emptive pitch schedule is exploited to ease the transition into above rated operation. The magnitude of the pitch angle is increased linearly from 1.5m/s below rated wind speed to 0.5m/s above rated.

Figure 12: Pitch strategies for the X-Rotor wind turbine concept

3.4 Above rated

To maintain a constant rotor speed in above rated conditions, the upper blades of the primary rotor are pitched to shed aerodynamic power. As the primary rotor tip speed ratio drops, the retarding torque from the secondary rotors increases on average due to the decrease in the primary rotor tip speed ratio, see (4). The consequences for the operation of the turbine are readily rectified through a small adjustment in the secondary rotor speed as the wind speed increases, which would be automatically accompanied by an adjustment to primary rotor pitch angle.

The structural damping of wind turbine blades is key for system stability. However, in higher wind speeds when the blades are pitched it becomes low and even negative over part of a rotor rotation. It is, thus, important that the blades are as possible kept flying to the extent that the net damping over a rotation is positive. As verified using dynamic simulations of the X-Rotor turbine, sufficient damping is obtained for pitching the blades to feather in the upwind half of a rotation. For this reason, nose out (negative) pitching is chosen as opposed to nose in (positive) pitching. The required pitch strategy is shown in Figure 12.

3.5 Above rated – Saturation control

As discussed in Section 2.3, the mean power captured by the secondary rotor increases as the primary rotor tip speed ratio reduces when operating in the above rated constant rotor speed mode.

This increase in power can be exploited to increase energy capture by the secondary rotors beyond that provided by the primary rotor. However, to avoid having to uprate the secondary rotor power-trains significantly, the mean power over a rotation of the primary rotor should be limited to a small percentage of rated power, say 6%. This extra power manifests itself as an oscillation in the power at the rotor frequency. However, in wind speeds when this limit would be exceeded, it can be prevented by restricting the amplitude in the secondary rotor speed oscillations over a rotation. Over each primary rotor rotation, the secondary rotors therefore follow four distinct operating modes. During its upwind sweep before the output power is above the allowed maximum, the upwind blade operates at a constant tip speed ratio; when power reaches its allowed maximum, the tip speed ratio is modified to hold the power constant; when the power drops below the maximum value again, the blade changes back to constant tip speed ratio operation; when the rotor is downwind, it operates at the same rotor speed as the upwind blade. For an incident windspeed of 21m/s, the fluctuations in rotor power and rotor speed are shown in Figure 13, and the mean and instantaneous torque speed curve for a single secondary rotor is shown in Figure 14.

Figure 13: Combined secondary rotor power output and secondary rotor speed at a windspeed of 21m/s

Figure 14: Secondary rotor torque speed behaviour at a windspeed of 22m/s

4 Definition of operational strategy for the X-Rotor

Figure 15 depicts the full control strategy for the X-Rotor wind turbine across each of the 5 operational zones. Figure 16 shows the power curve and associated deterministic power swings. The corresponding torque-speed plots are shown in Figures 17, 18 and 19.

In region 1, the above-design average tip speed ratio of the secondary rotors, and the consequent slight over-speeding of the primary rotor are clear. Despite this off-design operation, the turbine power coefficient remains relatively unchanged. The maximum power point tracking mode extends from 4.9m/s up to 10.5m/s. During maximum power point tracking, the secondary rotor operates with a nominal tip speed ratio of 3, resulting in an average tip speed ratio of 3.45 due to the above-nominal tip speed ratio operation over half the rotor cycle. The primary rotor is held at a tip speed ratio of 5. Pre-emptive pitching is employed between 10.5m/s and 12.m/s, with a slope of -5.3 °s/m. The full turbine therefore reaches rated power at 12.1m/s after the pre-emptive pitch regime is employed. The secondary rotors can continue operating in normal upwind tip speed ratio tracking up to 17.5m/s, when a power of 5.25MW (5% above the rated power) is reached. After this point, the peak power is capped by reducing the secondary rotor speed. This results in the mean operating point on the torque-speed plot, shown in figure 19, being shifted up and left at a secondary rotor speed of 45rad/s. The primary rotor speed and pitch angle and the mean secondary rotor speed and maximum instantaneous power and power output are given as a function of wind speed in Table 1. The secondary rotor speed as a function of windspeed and azimuth angle are given in Table 2.

Figure 15: Control strategy for the X-Rotor

Figure 16: Final power curve for the X-Rotor

Figure 17: Torque speed plot for the X-Rotor primary rotor

Figure 18: Secondary rotor retarding torque as a function of secondary rotor speed

Figure 19: Torque speed plot for a single X-Rotor secondary rotor

Wind speed [m/s]	Primary rotor speed [rad/s]	Primary rotor pitch [°]	Secondary rotor speed [rad/s]	Maximum power [MW]	Output power [MW]
3	0.21	0	17.66	-	0.08
4	0.27	0	17.66	-	0.19
5	0.33	0	17.96	-	0.36
6	0.40	0	21.56	-	0.63
7	0.47	0	25.15	-	1
8	0.53	0	28.74	-	1.49
9	0.60	0	32.34	-	2.13
10	0.67	0	35.93	-	2.92
11	0.73	-2.81	39.28	-	3.82
12	0.78	-8.09	42.05	-	4.7
13	0.80	-12.83	43.41	-	5.04
14	0.80	-14.22	43.81	-	5.08
15	0.80	-15.09	44.21	-	5.12
16	0.80	-15.92	44.62	-	5.17
17	0.80	-16.69	45.02	-	5.22
18	0.80	-17.49	44.58	5.65	5.26
19	0.80	-18.18	43.62	5.56	5.26
20	0.80	-18.88	43.01	5.52	5.26
21	0.80	-19.6	42.59	5.49	5.26
22	0.80	-20.27	42.3	5.47	5.26
23	0.80	-20.91	42.07	5.45	5.26
24	0.80	-21.47	41.87	5.43	5.26
25	0.80	-22.01	41.73	5.42	5.26

Table 1: Operating points for the X-Rotor

Rotor speed [rad/s]		Angle of Azimuth [°]								
		0,180	20,200	40,220	60,240	80,260	100,280	120,300	140,320	160,340
Wind speed [m/s]	3	15.8	16.8	17.7	18.4	18.7	18.7	18.4	17.7	16.8
	4	15.7	16.8	17.7	18.4	18.8	18.8	18.4	17.7	16.8
	5	16.0	17.0	18.0	18.7	19.1	19.1	18.7	18.0	17.0
	6	19.1	20.5	21.6	22.5	22.9	22.9	22.5	21.6	20.5
	7	22.3	23.9	25.2	26.2	26.7	26.7	26.2	25.2	23.9
	8	25.5	27.3	28.8	29.9	30.6	30.6	29.9	28.8	27.3
	9	28.7	30.7	32.4	33.7	34.4	34.4	33.7	32.4	30.7
	10	31.9	34.1	36.0	37.4	38.2	38.2	37.4	36.0	34.1
	11	34.9	37.3	39.4	41.0	41.8	41.8	41.0	39.4	37.3
	12	37.3	40.0	42.3	44.0	44.9	44.9	44.0	42.3	40.0
	13	38.2	41.0	43.5	45.4	46.4	46.4	45.4	43.5	41.0
	14	38.2	41.2	43.9	45.9	47.0	47.0	45.9	43.9	41.2
	15	38.2	41.5	44.3	46.5	47.6	47.6	46.5	44.3	41.5
	16	38.2	41.7	44.7	47.0	48.2	48.2	47.0	44.7	41.7
	17	38.2	41.9	45.2	47.6	48.9	48.9	47.6	45.2	41.9
	18	38.2	42.1	45.6	48.1	45.3	45.3	48.1	45.6	42.1
	19	38.2	42.3	46.0	46.4	42.5	42.5	46.4	46.0	42.3
	20	38.2	42.5	46.4	43.2	41.4	41.4	43.2	46.4	42.5
	21	38.2	42.8	46.8	41.9	40.8	40.8	41.9	46.8	42.8
	22	38.2	43.0	47.1	41.2	40.7	40.7	41.2	47.1	43.0
23	38.2	43.2	47.2	40.7	40.5	40.5	40.7	47.2	43.2	
24	38.2	43.4	44.5	40.6	40.5	40.5	40.6	44.5	43.4	
25	38.2	43.6	43.0	40.4	40.5	40.5	40.4	43.0	43.6	

Table 2: Secondary rotor speed in rad/s as a function of azimuth angle and wind speed

5 Conclusion

This report has described the development of the control strategy for the X-Rotor wind turbine. The primary rotor is controlled in a similar manner to a conventional HAWT rotor, and the blades are pitched to feather in the upwind rotor half in order to maintain sufficient aerodynamic damping in above rated conditions. The secondary rotors are operated so as to increase power capture whilst limiting the hardware requirements for the powertrain. The final rated windspeed of the turbine is 12.4m/s including the pre-emptive pitching of the primary rotor, and additional power is captured up to 17.5m/s by the interaction of the secondary rotors with the incident wind speed before the mean power is limited at 5% above the power rating of the generator.

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